

Tumaracatu: An Ubiquitous Digital Musical Experience of Maracatu

Danielle Lopes¹, Gilberto Bernardes^{1,2}, Luis Aly^{1,2}, Jorge Forero¹

¹Faculty of Engineering of Porto
Rua Dr. Roberto Frias, 4200-465 Porto – Portugal.

²Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science
Rua Dr. Roberto Frias, 4200-465 Porto – Portugal.

{dlopes7773@gmail.com}

Abstract. *We present Tumaracatu, an application for fostering a performative digital experience of maracatu. Our work’s main contributions are curating an adaptive user experience of maracatu with ubiquitous off-the-shelf technology and advancing a new digital shaker model using physics-based concatenative sound synthesis. We developed the application in PureData for both Android and iOS smartphone devices using MobMuPlat. A preliminary evaluation by expert maracatu performers has shown that Tumaracatu simultaneously serves as a performance, entertainment, and learning tool.*

1. Introduction

Maracatu is a ritualistic performance from Recife, Brazil, which combines dance, music, and religion. A rhythmic choreography of primitive expression, rooted in African traditions, centers on the embodiment of musical performance gestures and dance movements as inextricable manifestations [César 1955]. The percussive-only nature of maracatu music unravels in time as rhythmic variations from baseline patterns. Current maracatu practices adopt a combination of the following percussive instruments: gonguê, agbê, timbau, tarol or caixa de guerra, alfaias, and ganzá, also known as mineiro. Each instrument has a specific function in the resulting polyrhythm of the *baque*. The Portuguese word *baque* is widely used in the musical universe of Maracatu to mean beat, blow, or touch and will be used hereafter in its original language due to its idiosyncratic nature [César 1955]. The musical performance of maracatu is the *baque*. Moreover, this word is present in two types of Maracatu existing: Maracatu Nação (Baque Virado) and Maracatu Rural (Baque Solto). The differentiation between styles of each *baque* is made by musical characteristics that invoke sound quality and quantity. The quality explains the rhythm, timbre, harmony, and volume, classifying the different types of toques of the maracatu. The most observed distinction is the musical rhythm of each group, some slower and others faster. The Baque de Luanda and Baque de Arrasto are considered slower; and the de Martelo, faster [De Carvalho 2007]. The timbre is perceived mainly through the sound of the alfaias. Variations in timbre performed simultaneously by a group of alfaias are of primary importance to maintain rhythmic coherence [Albernaz and Oliveira 2015].

The quantity refers to the numerous maracatu groups, given the greater volume of the performance sound. Fundamental to the structure of Maracatu are three specific layers that can be related to the gonguê, ganzá, and alfaia instruments. Figure 1 shows some

prototypical rhythmic patterns for each of the above instruments. The rhythmic patterns were inspired by the first author own experience and musical practice with Maracatu.

Figure 1. Representative baseline and variations rhythmic patterns for the gonguê, ganzá, and alfaia instruments in maracatu.

The gonguê is the highest-pitched instrument in the baque. Its musical function is to establish the pulse by a uniform rhythmic pattern to which the remaining layers (and instruments) articulate polyrhythms [César 1955]. The instrument has two steel-cast iron grooves with different tones, called positive (lower tone) and negative (higher tone). The first is generated over the instrument’s body; the second is near the base [César 1955]. The ganzá is a cylindrically shaped idiophone instrument constructed as a hand-woven basket or a metal canister filled with beads, pebbles, or other similar items. It is played by shaking the arm to produce a rhythmic pattern that is typically steady, e.g., a set of four quarter notes with accents on the first and fourth notes, orally taught as TU-ma-ra-CA-TU. The alfaias are drums, traditionally made of barrels with animal skin, and produce the lowest-pitched tones in the baque. They provide the main rhythmic ‘melody’ and are typically in larger numbers, the so-called *batuqueiros*. A typically African organization of high, medium, and low alfaias are adopted and referred to as *repiques*, *meião*, and *marcantes*, respectively. The variations are rhythmic patterns created by the alfaias, which break the constant repetition of the beat by creating intricate polyrhythms. They are the faster patterns in maracatu and require a virtuosic movement of the arms.

The performers’ movements in maracatu summon different corporeality that occurs in synchronization with and response to the metric properties of the music. For example, arm movements required to play the ganzá will equally impact the movements of the lower limbs, such as the legs [Afonso 2017]. The performed movements accumulate musical, visual, social, and ritual functions. The pulse marking on the body unifies internal tempos, facilitates the execution of syncopated rhythms, creates a ‘music of the bodies,’ and defines visual references for instrumental execution [De Freitas 2009]. Based on the corporal importance of this ritualistic practice arises the primary rationale of our work: listening to maracatu does not capture the practice. Maracatu needs to be experienced as a music-dance ritualistic symbiosis.

Leveraging on current ubiquitous digital technology, we propose *Tumaracatu*, a digital mobile application to promote a performative maracatu experience. It relies on the accelerometer sensor of a handheld mobile device (e.g., smartphone) to drive the control of the physics-based concatenated sound synthesis of the ganzá and an adaptive map-

ping of alfaías and gonguê loops. The physical dynamics of user movement control the mechanics of the generated maracatu rhythmic patterns beyond a passive listening experience. While advancing on the maracatu experience using off-the-shelf ubiquitous technology [Friedewald and Raabe 2011], Tumaracatu encompasses a contribution at the sound synthesis level, which seeks a computationally efficient technique compromising the quality of the interaction control and sound synthesis. The remainder of the paper is structured as followed. Section 2 reviews related work along three main lines of research: the application of ubiquitous digital technology for augmenting musical experience and two of its main underlying mechanics: the physical interaction modalities and sound synthesis for digital music instruments. Section 3 details the proposed mobile application for maracatu experience. Section 4 provides some preliminary evaluation of the Tumaracatu prototype application, and Section 5 summarizes the main conclusions of our study and avenues for future work.

2. Related Work

The domain of the current study accounts for multiple areas of knowledge related to the design of digital musical instruments and its multiple implications in listening and musical practices, namely what concerns the embodiment of the musical control gesture and its sonic feedback. For example, when listening to music, the body responds to the stimulus and allows the mind to recognize the music according to the resulting physical interaction. This physical response is strengthened in instrumental music practice due to the interaction between the musician, the instrument and the feedback loop that is established [Jensenius et al. 2009]. In this context, musical gestures have different functions, such as communicating musical intentions or producing sound [Leman et al. 2008]. A parallel could be established to the conductor role in communicating with the orchestra through a specific set of gestures and the performer role, which execute gestures that produce sound. Next, we survey related lines of research to the above-identified musical intentional and sound-producing roles in the digital domain, namely on what concerns the physical interaction and synthesis models in digital musical instruments.

2.1. Physical interaction

Music and movement support each other during a musical performance, and the musical gesture is a visible indication of this intimate relation [Zelechowska et al. 2020]. People tend to associate musical gestures with different sound features [Eitan and Granot 2006]. Sound features such as dynamics (i.e., the difference between the highest and lowest amplitude peak) can be associated with a particular movement's speed. In short musical gestures facilitate music understanding and expression [Meimaridou et al. 2020].

A relevant area of knowledge to the purpose of our study is the control of musical instruments through air gestures. Traditional musical instruments are manipulated with physical contact through the body movement of specific parts, such as the hands. Electronic and digital instruments also require physical contact to actuate on a key or push a button to generate sound. An exception is the theremin [Theremin and Petrishev 1996], an instrument played with air gestures controlling pitch and volume as a result of the proximity to two antennas. More recently, with the advancement of motion sensing technologies, such direct physical connection has become more diffuse. Motion sensing in mobile devices promotes the musical exploration of digital instruments through a set of

meaningful movements performed *in the air* [Dahl 2015]. The author conducted a series of experiments on sensorimotor synchronization to understand what people do when performing air gestures in time to rhythmic sounds and how their movements correspond to the sounds. The results showed that acceleration peaks yield the best results in sensorimotor synchronization for a real-time musical system because they occur on average before the audio event and do not vary as much with note speed. In summary, the study revealed that people prefer to execute a movement first and hear sound next.

2.2. Sound Synthesis of Musical Shakers

The sound synthesis of the ganzá, a fundamental instrument to our work and a pervasive instrument across different music genres fits within the broad category of musical shaker. The digital sound synthesis of musical shakers has been prominently pursued by physical modeling synthesis emulations, which allow the generation of a variety of timbres and the intuitive parameterization of the algorithm to accommodate its multiple material size manifestations.

In [Cook 2002] presents the Physically-Informed Stochastic Event synthesis Model (PhISEM) containing several controllers, such as accelerometers or force-sensing resistors, generating MIDI data to parameters for a synthesis model which translates shaking and scraping gestures into sound. Based on this model, the author developed the *Haptic Maraca* [Cook 2003], which adds a haptic layer to reinforce the sound-gesture connection. The *bEADS Extended Actuated Digital Shaker* [Williams and Overholt 2017] expands the *Haptic Maraca* with a loudspeaker embedded and modeled after a shaker's generic form. The high computational expense of these digital instruments required an external computer to run the audio engine and the high complexity of the model in capturing the involved non-linear control gesture and sound response relationships. Moreover, these physical simulation challenges simplify the continuous-time model into a discrete approximation at the expense of the expressive realistic result. Recently, [Piepenbrink 2018] developed the *eShaker* and *eChocalho*, which are self-contained instruments, battery-powered, and can synthesize various shakers, rattles, and other handheld shaker percussion. Although the graphical user interface parameters and preset selection can be configured wireless through a computer program, the instrument has an embedded sound synthesis engine. More recently, there has been a development of commercial mobile applications of shakers. *The Salt Shaker* is a musical instrument built upon ideas of tangible and embodied interaction [Craig and Armen 2020]. It uses acceleration to encode shaking gestures into digital information, thereby translating these gestures into a rhythm and humanizing the digital audio synthesis process. Furthermore, commercial applications such as the music game *Shakers*¹ an Android application that emulates different with ten different percussion instruments, including a shaker; or the *RealShaker*² which explores a real shaker's dynamics and physicality as the user moves, tilt, and shake his device to generate sound.

3. Tumaracatu: A Digital Mobile Application for Maracatu Experience

The application Tumaracatu, named after the underlying phonetic accents used to learn the ganzá, aims to foster an performative digital experience of the maracatu practice beyond

¹<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.bti.shakers>

²<https://apps.apple.com/us/app/realshaker-highly-realistic-responsive-shaker-rattle/id1062454423>

passive listening. To this end, Tumaracatu mimics the ganzá music-movement expression from instantaneous user actions to create a digital ganzá shaker and provides two additional layers of gonguê and alfaia rhythmic patterns that gradually adapt to long-term user actions.

Figure 2. Architecture of the Tumaracatu application. Dashed lines isolate its two major components for physical interaction and sound synthesis. The solid rectangular blocks denote the processing blocks of the application. The flux of control data and audio signals is indicated as solid thick and bold arrows, respectively.

Tumaracatu was deployed as a mobile application for off-the-shelf handheld devices, namely smartphones running Android and iOS. Employing handheld devices, we target a broad audience which has facilitated access to these devices. Pure Data [Puckette et al. 1997] was adopted to design the application, which we later ported to mobile devices using MobMuPlat [Iglesia and Intermedia 2016]. The architecture of Tumaracatu is shown in Figure 2. It features two main modules for physical interaction and sound synthesis (dashed lines in Figure 2), each with two primary processing modules (solid rectangular blocks). User input gestures controlling a handheld device are captured by accelerometer sensor technology, embedded in the vast majority of current handheld devices on the market, and aim to promote a feedback loop between the user’s movements and the maracatu musical counterpart. In greater detail, the instantaneous and (long-term) averaged acceleration magnitude is used to control two sound synthesis processes: ganzá physics-based concatenative sound synthesis and the adaptive loop-based gonguê and alfaia playback.

3.1. Handheld physical interaction: Capturing Performative Gestures

To capture user input gestures, we use the triaxial accelerometers embedded in handheld mobile devices. Accelerometers are technological devices that allow obtaining a measurement of linear acceleration in a certain spatial axis. There are various mechanisms to measure this magnitude. Common strategies adopt mechanical (dynamometers), electromechanical (piezoelectric), electrical (capacitors), or magnetic (hall effect) components. Accelerometers in handheld devices are often embedded in chips to measure acceleration for each spatial dimension (x, y, z). Although each chip computes the mechanical, electrical, or magnetic transduction to obtain the magnitude of the acceleration in each axis, according to the manufacturer’s own criteria, accelerometers usually report the acceleration based on the acceleration of gravity (g) on the planet earth ($1g = 9.81m/s^2$), in a range between $\pm 2g$ and $\pm 24g$. In both cases, the chips can typically sample acceleration in the range between 100 MHz and 400 MHz. For example, the default accelerometer sample rate on an iOS devices is the range $\pm 2g$ at 100MHz with a nominal resolution of 0.018g. In the $\pm 8g$ range, the resolution would be four times higher [Allan 2011].

To capture the accelerometer data, we adopted MobMuPlat, which normalizes data to the range ± 1 at a sampling rate of $\approx 100\text{Hz}$ (iOS) and $\approx 20\text{Hz}$ (Android). To account for velocity changes over time regardless of the direction in space, we calculated the magnitude of the triaxial accelerometer data using the Euclidean norm from the sensor data. Following [Van Hees et al. 2013], to separate movement and gravity components in the acceleration data, we subtract to the norm one. This strategy allows the acceleration magnitude value to be invariant to the device’s spatial position. The resulting value is considered our instantaneous acceleration magnitude, which controls the ganzá. An average value across a sliding window of 5 seconds provides a long-term indicator of user movement, which we adopt to control the loop-based variations of the alfaías and gongüê.

3.2. Physical Ganzá Control and Synthesis

To digitally emulate the continuous sonic interaction of the ganzá, we adapt the physics-based concatenative synthesis (PBCS), a recently proposed technique by [Magalhães et al. 2020] to model the interaction and synthesis of rolling objects. The motivation to adopt PBCS is due to 1) the expressive potential of the technique for fostering a high degree of correspondence across the physical and the experienced interaction, as it enforces, by design, the perceptual congruence through the capture and rendering from realistic sources; 2) the exemption of cumbersome mappings across input gesture and its sonic feedback; 3) its time and space computational efficiency.

Figure 3. Architecture of the physics-based concatenative synthesis of the ganzá. Rectangular blocks indicate the main processing modules and arrows denote the data flux (dashed lines for control data and solid lines for audio signals).

Figure 3 shows the architecture of the proposed PBCS framework. It includes two major capture and synthesis components. The capture component assembles an annotated *corpus* of ganzá *units* of about $t = 93$ ms (i.e. 4096 sample window at 44.1 kHz sampling rate). Each unit is annotated with a value of acceleration magnitude. To collect the annotated corpus, a synchronous recording of audio and acceleration magnitude data was conducted. A single acceleration magnitude value per unit duration is adopted by averaging all values across the unit duration. An important design feature of the PBCS capture

is collecting sound grains for the most comprehensive array of acceleration magnitude values in the smallest duration for efficient computational memory space management. The audio and acceleration captured data consisted of ≈ 30 seconds including a large set of typical ganzá gestures (e.g., *toque seco* and *cambinda* – see Figure 1 a musical notated representation of these rhythms), silence, and free exploration of movements at various velocities.

Figure 4 shows the captured audio and acceleration magnitude data of a ganzá gesture. Of note is the non-linear relation between the two signals, which are typically misrepresented in techniques that manually enforce these relationships, such as in physical modeling. A great advantage of PBCS is the modeling of both control gestures and their resulting sonic feedback.

Figure 4. Synchronous audio and acceleration magnitude data for a maracatu toque seco gesture from the captured session.

The synthesis module generates the auditory feedback by concatenating short audio units from a corpus of ganzá recordings. The selection of a temporal sequence of units to be concatenated is driven by a target defining at each $t/2$ (i.e., an overlap of two sample windows). The real-time magnitude acceleration data defines the targets. In the feature space, audio units stemming from the same physical conditions during the capture stage result in neighbourhood locations. In other words, we ascertain that sound grains with similar acceleration magnitude values have a perceptual resemblance, thus a smaller distance in the feature space. Furthermore, audio source signals and annotations are captured in the same conditions as the rendering stage. Thereby, audio units' annotations and online target feature vector navigation occurs in the same feature space.

3.3. Gonguê and Alfaias Adaptive Loop-based Variations

To emulate the ritualistic character of the maracatu performance in terms of embodied expression, we adopt a (long-term) average acceleration magnitude to adapt a set of loops for the gonguê and alfaias. The audio loops for each instrument were designed to account for different degrees of density and complexity. The rhythmic patterns adopted are shown in Figure 1. The starting loops (numbered as loop 0) of gonguê and alfaias establish a baseline pattern that defines the pulse. Once the user starts interacting with the application and gradually evolve the ganzá rhythms, the alfaias and gonguê loops are equally adapted to respond to the continuous experience. The climax of adaptation results in a more dense rhythmic pattern with an intricate polyrhythmic structure and greater tonal

components resulting from the addition of a larger set of pitched (repique and meia) alfaias. Figure 5, shows the mapping between acceleration magnitude values (normalized to the [0-1] range) and the loops of the gonguê and alfaias.

Figure 5. Adaptive Mappings between normalized acceleration magnitude values and the gonguê and alfaias loops. The numbering of the loops correspond to those shown in Figure 1.

The gonguê and alfaia loops were sequenced from existing recordings of maracatu de baque solto collected in a previous study [Davies et al. 2020]. Before the loop sequence, we isolated gonguê alfaia notes resulting from a large set of percussive strokes. Then, we arranged the sequences to comply with the rhythmic pattern shown in Figure 1, namely their accents and tone variation. Finally, we adjusted the loops using micro-timing deviations for accounting layered interaction.

We created three gonguê loops. Gonguê loop 0 established a baseline pulse, and it is widely adopted across many maracatu expressions and one of the most traditional patterns. Nação Elefante and Leão Coroado adopt this pattern. Gonguê loop 1, expand the set of tones notes a twofold higher and lower notes. The lower notes represent the ‘attack’ accented sound, and the higher notes can be understood as their response. This gonguê pattern is adopted by Nação Porto Rico. The gonguê loop 2 mixes the two previous loops to create an intricate response when combined with loop 2 of the alfaias (i.e., the martelo variation). For the alfaias, we created four loops. Alfaia loop 0 establishes the traditional *marcação* or baseline pulse, which all maracatu nations adopt when performing the alfaia with the right-hand only. The alfaia loop 1 is the *marcação* plus a convention. This convention will usually be repeated in the presentation being originated by the Nação Estrela. The alfaia loop 2 adopts the repique drums playing the *martelo* of Nação Estrela Brilhante do Recife, a rhythm known to be more accelerated. The alfaia loop 3 adopts marcante drums playing a bass pattern and alfaia meia drums playing the *arrasto* variation, resulting in a highly dense rhythmic pattern.

4. Evaluation

We conducted a preliminary qualitative evaluation to assess the musical affordances of Tumaracatu. Particular emphasis is given to the inextricable input and output (sonic feedback) modules of the application for the digital synthesis of the ganzá. Collected feedback will be used to improve the future design iterations of Tumaracatu. In greater detail, the evaluation consisted of a task-based online experiment followed by an interview. A purposive sampling of participants with previous musical expertise with maracatu and, in particular, of the ganzá in a baque was adopted. To reach eligible participants, we establish direct contacts with personal acquaintances and their network of performers to widen the sociodemographic of the sample.

4.1. Procedure

The conducted experiment had a threefold phase structure. The first phase aimed to install the application on the device and create some degree of familiarity with its mechanics. In greater detail, once user installed the application, they were asked questions about the maracatu universe and their experiences as a musician. Then the user was invited to experiment with the ganzá alone for about two minutes freely. No prior instruction was provided.

The second phase of the experiment included the completion of two tasks. The first task consisted of sequentially performing the cambinda, toque seco and tumaracatu rhythmic patterns (see Figure 1) ganzá with the application. No tempo, i.e., beats per minute (bpm), was imposed for the task, and for each pattern, participants could explore the rhythm for about two minutes. In the second task, participants were given the same instructions to be performed with the additional gonguê and alfaia rhythmic patterns and adaptive mechanics. Besides providing an encompassing backing track for the maracatu, the additional layers also aimed at further constraining the user to the given tempo, 90 bpm. This twofold design aimed at having participants approach the experiment in two different ways with increasing degrees of constraints, namely in terms of the tempo, which was imposed in the second task by the underlying gonguê and alfaia patterns.

In the third phase of the experiment, we conducted a semi-structured interview. By promoting an informal conversation with the participants, we prioritize their most immediate impressions and concerns about Tumaracatu. The protocol was also prone to guide the participant in providing specific details about: the implications of different rhythmic pattern densities in the sonic feedback of the ganzá and the recognition of the adopted rhythmic layers and instruments following the participant's practice.

4.2. Results

Three experienced musicians in the practice of maracatu completed the experiment (two females and one male participant aged between 28 and 25). Two participants used IOS, iPhone 6 and iPhone 11 PRO. Furthermore, one participant used Android, Samsung A8. All participants are active maracatu performers with at least eight years of performance practice. In the third phase of the experiment, we recorded a semi-structured interview for transcription purposes, for which consent by the participant was collected.

The participants were able to understand the underlying mechanics of the Tumaracatu, with few to no prior explanations, and were able to complete both proposed tasks. However, an overall comment on the need for an adaptation phase to learn finer degrees of control of the ganzá was pinpointed. Therefore, the results suggest some learning curve towards expressive performance. One participant highlighted difficulties in playing ganzá on a mobile handheld device due to its reduced dimensions compared to the acoustic instrument. All participants reported an overall enjoyment in conducting the experiment, mainly in phase two, where the gonguê and alfaia instruments were added.

Participants reported high degrees of control in performing the cambinda rhythm and toque seco. All participants reported challenges keeping a specific tempo with the ganzá without the two remaining gonguê and alfaia layers. Overall, the interaction of the ganzá and the alfaia was perceived as the most challenging. The participant using an Android device found greater difficulty controlling the cambinda pattern, which requires

greater degrees of freedom than the *toque seco*. The same behaviour was not perceived by participants adopting iOS devices. This behaviour is probably related to the rate at which the sensor data was acquired. Further research on the implications of each device's sensor technology and signal processing techniques should shed light on perceived differences.

One participant recalled that the *ganzá* is an instrument that requires an advanced performance technique, fundamental to the overall stability of the *baque*, namely in establishing a pulse. To this end, we conducted the tasks to pursue the right pulse, which aligns with the rhythmic pattern *toque seco*. In sum, the feedback collected from using Tumaracatu suggests it captures to a particular degree the challenges inherent to the acoustic practice of the *ganzá*, and that somehow the experience of performing *maracatu* was recollected in the digital domain.

5. Conclusions and Future Work

In this paper, we presented Tumaracatu, an application deployed as a mobile application for off-the-shelf handheld devices, namely smartphones running Android and iOS. The main goal of Tumaracatu is the digital emulation of the experience of *maracatu*, a ritualistic performance that inextricably combines dance music and religion. To this end, an experience of the *ganzá* performative gesture was our primary direction. In this context, two main contributions resulted from our work: 1) a physics-based concatenative synthesis model of the *ganzá* and 2) a curated digital experience for *maracatu* offering the possibility to experience the *maracatu* through a handheld mobile device. The code and multiple performance examples with the Tumaracatu, can be found online at <https://bit.ly/3tR84Gf>.

A preliminary evaluation of Tumaracatu consisting of a task-based experiment followed by a semi-structured interview was conducted with three expert musicians. Particular emphasis was given to the performance with the *ganzá* and its interaction with the remaining layers of *gonguê* and *alfaia* adaptive loops. Ultimately, the feedback collected during the experiment aimed to improve future iterations of Tumaracatu. Participants reported high degrees of control in performing both the *cambinda* and *toque seco* rhythmic pattern. The experiment denoted some challenges concerning the iteration of the *ganzá* with the remaining instruments, namely when the density of the rhythmic patterns increased. We can conclude that Tumaracatu provides a digital application to learn, perform and experience *maracatu*, beyond passive listening.

In the future, we aim to improve the design of Tumaracatu to tackle some identified limitations in the experiments: understand the different performance across iOS and Android devices and the fluency of gestures concerning sonic feedback. Future user studies shall equally inform optimal parameterization of the PBCS of the *ganzá*, namely the optimal unit duration, source requirements in terms of variation and duration for enhanced realism approximations and accurate sonic interaction. Finally, we will research novel mappings between sonic feedback and biosignals as control structures to promote an embodied experience of *maracatu* in the digital domain. Based on the biosignals' response, we intend to promote the creation of a feedback loop between the user's body and musical performance to reprogram the sound experience of that universe from an individual corporal perspective.

Acknowledgments

Research was partially funded by the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology, grant number: PD/BD/142892/2018 and the project “Experimentation in music in Portuguese culture: History, contexts and practices in the 20th and 21st centuries” (POCI-01-0145-FEDER-031380) co-funded by the European Union through the Operational Program Competitiveness and Internationalization, in its ERDF component, and by national funds, through the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology.

References

- Afonso, B. G. (2017). Olha o maracatu que lindo, sustenta a pisada no tambor maior! – dança e ritmo no grupo maracatu bloco de pedra. Master’s thesis, *Universidade Federal de São Paulo*.
- Albernaz, L. S. F. and Oliveira, J. M. (2015). Sinfonia de tambores: comunicação e estilos musicais no maracatu nação de pernambuco. *Revista Antropológicas*, 26(1).
- Allan, A. (2011). *Basic sensors in IOS: Programming the accelerometer, gyroscope, and more*. O’Reilly Media, Inc.
- César, G.-P. (1955). *Maracatus do recife*. São Paulo, *Irmãos Vitale Editora*.
- Cook, P. (2003). Remutualizing the instrument: Co-design of synthesis algorithms and controllers. In *Proceedings of the 2003 Stockholm Music and Acoustics Conference, SMAC*, pages 677–680.
- Cook, P. R. (2002). *Real sound synthesis for interactive applications*. CRC Press.
- Craig, E. and Armen, H. (2020). The salt shaker: Embodied interaction in a digital synthesis interface.
- Dahl, L. (2015). Comparing the timing of movement events for air-drumming gestures. In *International Symposium on Computer Music Multidisciplinary Research, CMMR*, pages 3–21. Springer.
- Davies, M. E., Fuentes, M., Fonseca, J., Aly, L., Jerónimo, M., Baraldi, F. B., and CUSP, M. (2020). Moving in time: Computational analysis of microtiming in maracatu de baque solto. In *21st International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference, ISMIR*.
- De Carvalho, E. (2007). Diálogo de negros, monólogo de brancos: transformações e apropriações musicais no maracatu de baque virado. Master’s thesis, *Universidade Federal de Pernambuco*.
- De Freitas, E. M. C. (2009). O gesto musical nos métodos de percussão afro-brasileira.
- Eitan, Z. and Granot, R. Y. (2006). How music moves:: Musical parameters and listeners images of motion. *Music perception*, 23(3):221–248.
- Friedewald, M. and Raabe, O. (2011). Ubiquitous computing: An overview of technology impacts. *Telematics and Informatics*, 28(2):55–65.
- Iglesia, D. and Intermedia, I. (2016). The mobility is the message: The development and uses of mobmuplat. In *Pure Data Conference (PdCon16)*. New York.

- Jensenius, A. R., Wanderley, M. M., Godøy, R. I., and Leman, M. (2009). Musical gestures: concepts and methods in research. *Musical gestures: Sound, movement, and meaning*, 12:12–35.
- Leman, M. et al. (2008). *Embodied music cognition and mediation technology*. MIT press.
- Magalhães, E., Jacob, J., Nilsson, N., Nordahl, R., and Bernardes, G. (2020). Physics-based concatenative sound synthesis of photogrammetric models for aural and haptic feedback in virtual environments. In *2020 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces Abstracts and Workshops (VRW)*, pages 376–379. IEEE.
- Meimaridou, E.-C., Athanasopoulos, G., and Cambouropoulos, E. (2020). Musical gestures: An empirical study exploring associations between dynamically changing sound parameters of granular synthesis with hand movements. In *Proceedings of the 14th International Symposium on Computer Music Multidisciplinary Research, CMMR*, page 880.
- Piepenbrink, A. (2018). Embedded digital shakers: Handheld physical modeling synthesizers. In *Proceedings of the 2018 conference on new interfaces for musical expression, NIME*, pages 362–363.
- Puckette, M. S. et al. (1997). Pure data. In *Proceedings of the 1997 International Computer Music Conference, ICMC*, pages 224–227.
- Theremin, L. S. and Petrishev, O. (1996). The design of a musical instrument based on cathode relays. *Leonardo Music Journal*, 6(1):49–50.
- Van Hees, V. T., Gorzelniak, L., Leon, E. C. D., Eder, M., Pias, M., Taherian, S., Ekelund, U., Renström, F., Franks, P. W., Horsch, A., et al. (2013). Separating movement and gravity components in an acceleration signal and implications for the assessment of human daily physical activity. *PloS one*, 8(4):e61691.
- Williams, P. L. and Overholt, D. (2017). beads: Extended actuated digital shaker. In *Proceedings of the 2017 conference on new interfaces for musical expression, NIME*, pages 13–18. NIME.
- Zelechowska, A., Gonzalez Sanchez, V. E., Laeng, B., Vuoskoski, J. K., and Jensenius, A. R. (2020). Who moves to music? empathic concern predicts spontaneous movement responses to rhythm and music. *Music & Science*, 3:1–16.